

The Role of Institutional Ownership as Moderating Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Programs on Corporate Values

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the effect of Corporate Social Responsibility on Firm Value with Institutional Ownership as a moderating variable in mining companies. This study uses the population of mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2015-2017. Sampling using a purposive sampling technique and samples obtained by 10 companies. The analytical method used is quantitative using SPSS 15.0. The results of this study indicate that Corporate Social Responsibility has a negative effect on Company Value. The results of the Institutional Ownership research on Company Value have a positive effect which means it can moderate CSR on Company Value. This positive relationship shows that the increase in Institutional Ownership has an impact on the strengthened level of control exercised by shareholders on managerial behavior aimed at reducing agency costs and increasing Company Value.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Company Value, and Institutional Ownership

I. INTRODUCTION

In this increasingly advanced age, the need for energy also continues to grow. The mining sector is one of the pillars of economic development of a country, because of its role as a provider of energy resources that are indispensable for a country's economic growth. The nature and characteristics of the mining sector differ from other sectors. In the mining sector requires a very large investment cost, long-term, very risky, and the high uncertainty makes the problem of funding as a problem related to company development (Ningrum, 2015).

Stocks are one of the capital market instruments that investors are most interested in because they provide attractive returns. Shares can be defined as a sign of capital participation by one or one party (business entity) in a company or limited liability company. High stock prices make the value of the company also high, and increase market confidence not only in the company's current performance but also in the company's future prospects. This is because the value of the company is investors' perceptions of the company's success rate is often associated with stock prices. Mining sector shares recorded the highest growth this year. The mining sector index increased by 21.56% until 9 October 2018. According to Keown (2010) the value of the company is the market value of the company's debt and equity. Company value is the investor's perception of the company, which is often associated with stock prices. High stock prices make the value of the company is also high. Maximizing the value of the company is very important for a company because maximizing the value of the company also maximizes the prosperity of shareholders which is the company's main goal. Increasing company value is a long-term goal of the company. Jensen (2001) states that in order to maximize the value of the company in the long run, managers are required to make decisions that consider all stakeholders, where managers will be evaluated for their performance based on their success in achieving their goals.

A company including a mining company must be able to control the financial potential and non-financial potential in increasing company value for the company's long-term existence. Maximizing the value of the company is very important for a company because maximizing the value of the company also maximizes the prosperity of shareholders which is the company's main goal. To measure company value, there are several ratios that can be used, one of which is Price Book Value (PBV). Price Book Value is a measurement of market performance against book value (Mardiyanto, 2009). Based on this, the Mining Company Stock Value is as follows:

Table 1. Firm Value for 2015-2017

Firm Value	2015	2016	2017
Price Book Value	1,16	1,67	2,70

Source: IDX website

The value of Mining Companies in 2015-2017 has increased, due to several things, namely, corporate action and projected company performance in the future. The interest of several issuers towards mining companies caused many CSR programs to be carried out.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept and action taken by a company as a sense of responsibility towards the society and the environment in which the company stands. According to Daniri in Riswari and Cahyonowati (2012), CSR as an idea, companies are no longer faced with responsibilities that are grounded in a single bottom line, namely the value of the company (corporate value) which is reflected in its financial condition (financial) only, but corporate responsibility must stand on the triple bottom lines. Here, other bottom lines besides financial are social and environmental. So that CSR which was originally voluntary needs to be upgraded to CSR which is more mandatory.

The development of CSR implementation in Indonesia is marked by the number of companies implementing CSR, one of which is a mining company. Mining companies are known as environmental polluters. Therefore, many mining companies are implementing CSR to reduce the impact of environmental damage from their mining businesses. CSR in mining is different from CSR in other industries, such as banking, telecommunications, and so on, because CSR mining must be in accordance with the Environmental Impact and Analysis (AMDAL) of each mining company, which has been approved by the government.

Research related to the influence of CSR on company value was conducted by Ramadhani (2012), Nahda and Harjito (2011) stating that CSR has a positive effect on firm value. Different results shown by Romana (2017) and Puspaningrum (2017), indicate that CSR has no effect on firm value. Based on the results of research on the influence of CSR on firm value shows a difference, so it is interesting to do a re-study by adding a moderating variable, namely Institutional Ownership.

Institutional ownership is a stock of companies owned by institutions or institutions such as insurance companies, banks, investment companies, and institutional ownership. Institutional ownership is the percentage of shares owned by people outside the company of the total shares of the company. A high level of institutional stock will result in more intensive supervisory efforts so as to limit managers' opportunistic behavior, ie managers report earnings opportunistically to maximize their personal interests (Suryonugroho, 2016).

Based on the description above, the researcher intends to retest previous research conducted by Laras Surya Ramadhani (2012) on manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2010-2011. The difference of this research lies in moderating variables, samples and research years, namely in mining companies in 2015-2017. With the interest to get an understanding of the problem so that the solution will be obtained later.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a mechanism for a company to voluntarily integrate environmental and social attention into its options and interactions with stakeholders, which exceeds organizational responsibility in the legal field (Darwin 2004, in 2006 2006). Hackston and Milne in Sembiring (2005) mention the disclosure of corporate social responsibility or often called social disclosure is the process of communicating the social and environmental impacts of the organization's economic activities on special groups with an interest in society as a whole. There are mandatory disclosures, namely the disclosure of information required by companies that are based on certain regulations or standards, and some are voluntary which is the disclosure of additional information from the company.

The value of the company

Brigham and Gapenski (2006) in Ramadhani and Hadiprajitno (2012) stated that the value of the company is very important because high company value will be followed by high shareholder prosperity. Investors use financial ratios to find out the company's market value. This ratio can give an indication for the company regarding investors' assessment of the company's past performance and future prospects. There are several ratios that can be used to measure a company's market value, including the price earning ratio (PER) and the price to book value ratio (PBV). The price-earnings ratio is the ratio between a stock with earnings per share of the stock in question. And the price to book value ratio is a measurement of market performance against the book value (Mardiyanto, 2009).

Institutional Ownership

Institutional ownership is a stock of companies owned by institutions or institutions such as insurance companies, banks, investment companies, and institutional ownership. Institutional ownership is the percentage of shares owned by people outside the company of the total shares of the company. A high level of institutional stock will result in more intensive supervisory efforts so as to limit managers' opportunistic behavior, ie managers report earnings opportunistically to maximize their personal interests (Suryonugroho, 2016).

III. DATA, VARIABLES, AND METHODOLOGY

Population and Sample

Population (population) is the whole group of people, events, or things that researchers want to investigate. The population of this study is companies that carry out CSR programs for 3 consecutive years and are listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Data collection techniques used to obtain data in this study is with internet research (online research), namely observation data collection with secondary data in the form of annual financial reports contained in mining companies listed on the Stock Exchange published in IDX 2016-2018.

Expansion of Research Variables

Independent Variable

An index of the level of corporate social responsibility disclosure is measured by the ratio of the total score obtained by the maximum score obtained.

$$\text{Indeks} = \frac{n}{k}$$

n: number of disclosure scores obtained

k: maximum score

Moderating Variable

Institutional ownership symbolized by (X2), with the formula:

$$\text{Institutional ownership} = \frac{\text{shares owned by the institution}}{\text{outstanding shares}} \times 100\%$$

Dependent Variable

Company value can be seen through market value or the book value of a company and its equity

$$\text{PBV} = \frac{\text{market price per share}}{\text{book value per share}}$$

Analysis Method

Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA), which is to test whether moderating variables can strengthen independent variables against the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2011).

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + e$$

Figure 1. Regression Equation Model

Pure moderator equation:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 (X_1 * X_2) + e$$

Figure 2. Moderation Equation Model

α: constant

β1, β2, β3: regression coefficients

X1: Corporate Social Responsibility

X2: Institutional Ownership

X1 * X2: Interaction between Corporate Social Responsibility and Institutional Ownership

Y: Company Value

e: error or residue

IV. RESULTS

4.1. Research result

1. Model Feasibility Test (Test F)

The F test aims to determine whether or not the regression model is feasible between the Corporate Social Responsibility variables, Institutional Ownership of the Company Value variable. F test is done by looking at the significant value in the ANOVA table. If the significance is less than 0.05 then the model is appropriate to use.

Table2. ANOVA (b)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.352	3	4.451	3.409	.032(a)
	Residual	33.941	26	1.305		
	Total	47.293	29			

a Predictors: (Constant), CSR (X1) * INSTITUTIONAL OWNERSHIP (X2), INSTITUTION OWNERSHIP (X2), CSR (X1)

b Dependent Variable: PBV (Y)

From the ANOVA test in table 2, the calculated F value is 3.409 with a sig F value of 0.032 $< \alpha$ 0.05, so the model developed is feasible. This means that Corporate Social Responsibility and Institutional Ownership contribute to the Value of the Company.

2. Determination Coefficient Results

The coefficient of determination (R²) obtained in this study is 0,200 (20%). This shows that Corporate Value (Y) is influenced by 20% by Corporate Social Responsibility (X1), Institutional Ownership (X2), and interactions between Corporate Social Responsibility (X1) and Institutional Ownership (X2). While the remaining 80% is influenced by other variables outside the model under study.

3. Hypothesis Testing

Corporate Social Responsibility (X1)

The first hypothesis testing, there is the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility (X1) on Company Value (Y) With the regression coefficient marked negative indicates a negative relationship. The t value of the CSR variable count is -2,146 with a beta coefficient level of -0.416 $< \alpha$ 0.05 meaning H_a is accepted.

Institutional Ownership as a Moderation Variable (X2)

The second hypothesis testing, there is a relationship between the interaction of Corporate Social Responsibility (X1) and Institutional Ownership (X2) of Corporate Social Responsibility (X1) on Corporate Value (Y). In this case, Institutional Ownership (X2) is said to be the moderating variable of influence Corporate Social Responsibility (X1) on Company Value (Y). Because the value of positive interactions can be said that Institutional Ownership (X2) is a pseudo moderator, which indicates that the higher the value of Institutional Ownership (X2), will result in a higher influence of Corporate Social Responsibility (X1) on Corporate Value (Y). Based on the results of the analysis, the calculated t value of 2.451 with coefficient B of 0.433 $> \alpha$ 0.05 means that H_a is rejected.

4.2. Discussion of Research Results

Effect of Corporate Social Responsibility on Company Value

Based on the results of the analysis shows that corporate social responsibility has a negative effect on the value of the company in mining sector companies listed on the Stock Exchange in 2015-2017. The results of this study indicate that

the size of corporate social responsibility disclosure by the company does not affect the increase in firm value. The results of this study do not provide empirical support that companies that have implemented CSR and disclose their social responsibility information more broadly will have high corporate value.

The results of this study indicate that the company did not communicate corporate social responsibility appropriately so that it had not been received appropriately by the parties concerned. The results of this study are in line with Puspasingrum (2017) which concluded that CSR on firm value has a negative and not significant effect. Ramadhani, et al (2017) which states that Corporate Social Responsibility has a positive and significant effect on company value. This can be interpreted that the company is not only responsible to shareholders, but also to stakeholders. The benefits received by stakeholders will provide reciprocity for the company, such as trust and satisfaction.

The results of this study do not support theories that underlie the implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), namely agency theory and legitimacy theory. The company has not been oriented to the interests of stakeholders but is still oriented towards the interests of shareholders. The issuance of Law No. 25 of 2007 concerning Investment and Law Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies (Law on PT) has not fully influenced the implementation of CSR in mining sector companies consistently, namely for three periods of observation.

The Effect of Corporate Social Responsibility with Institutional Ownership on Company Value

Based on the results of the analysis shows that institutional ownership can strengthen the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on the value of the company in mining sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2015-2017. The results of this study indicate that an increase in institutional ownership has an impact on the strengthened level of control by shareholders on managerial behavior aimed at reducing agency costs and increasing firm value. Institutional ownership which is the majority owner is in favor of management and does not lead to personal interests so as not to neglect minority shareholders, this is responded positively by the market. This, in turn, leads to various efforts to reduce the level of fraud and fraud committed by management as a form of opportunistic actions. This study is not in line with research conducted by Suryonugroho (2017) which states that institutional ownership is not able to moderate company value.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

Corporate Social Responsibility has a negative and significant influence on the value of the company in mining sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2015-2017. The results of this study indicate that the size of corporate social responsibility disclosure by the company does not affect the increase in firm value. Institutional ownership strengthens the influence of corporate social responsibility on company value in mining sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2015 - 2017. So that the company can still maintain and improve the CSR programs that have been carried out. Companies that get low CSR scores can add CSR programs that can increase the number of investors.

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